

Quantitative Screening of *Corchoriosolitorius* and the Effects of Methanol Extract of *Corchoriosolitorius* on Hematological Indices and Electrolytes of Wistar rats

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Abstract: This study shows the quantitative screening of *Corchoriosolitorius* and the effects of methanolic extract of *Corchoriosolitorius* leaves on hematological indices and electrolytes of wistar rats. **Methods:** A total of thirty adult wistar rats weighing 85-110g were randomly divided into five groups, with 6 rats each respectively in each of the group. Normal control was administered with distilled water Group A to D was administered 100mg/kg, 150mg/kg, 250mg/kg, and 300mg/kg respectively of the plant extract. The extraction and all biochemical analysis were carried out using standard laboratory techniques. This experiment lasted for 14 days, and the hematological indices of wistar rats administered with *Corchoriosolitorius* leaves extract were investigated. **Results:** It was evident that administration of rats with *Corchoriosolitorius* leaves extract caused significant changes at ($p < 0.05$) in the white blood cell count (WBC) of the administered groups compared to the normal control group due to the extract. However, the administered group showed no significant increase in packed cell volume (PCV) compared to the control, this is because of the non toxic nature of the plant. The chloride concentration in groups A, B, C, and E administered 100, 150, 250 and 300 mg/kg b.w. of the extract, respectively, was not significant at ($p < 0.05$) compared to the normal control group. There was a non-significant difference at ($p < 0.05$) in potassium concentration when compared to the control group. The concentration of sodium in groups A, B, C, and D administered 100, 150, 250, and 300 mg/kg b.w. of the extract, respectively, was significant at ($p < 0.05$) compared with the normal group. Also this research investigated the phytochemical constituent of the extract and the result of the phytochemical screening showed that *Corchoriosolitorius* leaves contained appreciable amount of metabolite such as tannins, terpenoids, phenols and quinones are present in high quantity while steroid was available in low quantity. **Conclusion:** The study recommended that *Corchoriosolitorius* leaves be given to pregnant women with low blood count, and anemic patients as it helps in increasing blood volume.

Keywords: Medicinal plant, haematology, electrolytes, phytochemicals, treatment.

1. Introduction

Plants are an essential source of medication and play a crucial role in global health. Medicinal plants have been a significant source of possible treatments. Medicinal plants are now widely used in health systems all over the world, not only for disease treatment but also as a possible substance for maintaining good health (Oladeji O., 2016). Medicinal plants are plants that are commonly employed

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in the treatment and prevention of various maladies and diseases and are typically thought to be detrimental to humans. These plants are either "Wild plant species," which grow spontaneously in self-sustaining populations in natural and semi-natural ecosystems and can exist without direct human intervention, or "Domesticated plant species," which arose through human intervention such as selection or breeding and rely on management for survival (Oladeji O., 2016).

Modern research on herbal plants has led to considerable breakthroughs in the pharmacological evaluation of many plants used in traditional medical systems. Therefore, plants are the principal source of medicines, both as isolated active principles to be supplied in standardized dosage form and as crude pharmaceuticals for the general people (Oladeji O., 2016).

Secondary metabolites or substances found in medicinal plants, such as tannins, alkaloids, and flavonoids, determine the therapeutic effectiveness of the plants, particularly their antibacterial activity.

Chemical components in medicinal plants determine their therapeutic potency. Researchers have demonstrated several bioactive components at various doses. The therapeutic effectiveness of medicinal plants increases as the amount of an important phytochemical increase. In Nigeria, there are about 300 medicinal plants; nevertheless, the applications differ from plant to plant, culture to culture, whether and other circumstances (Oladeji O., 2016).

Jute leaf (*Corchorus olitorius*), popularly called ewedu among the Yoruba, ahinghara in Igbo and rama in Hausa, is a popular vegetable in West Africa. The botanical name is *Corchorus olitorius* (Fam: Malvaceae). Ewedu contains almost all of the nutrients needed by humans. It is rich in carotenoids, vitamins A C, B, K, Folic acid, calcium, potassium and iron and dietary fibers. It is also rich in both essential and non-essential amino acid, such as lysine. The leaves and young shoots are consumed. *Corchorus olitorius* can be boiled (alone or with locust beans, lemon, or olive oil), dried, steamed, or pureed, combined with chicken, or made into a soup. Soups, stews, teas, and vegetable dishes are flavored using jute leaves. In soups, dried leaves can be used as a thickening. In salads, young leaves are included. The leaves and roots can be made into cold infusions or decoctions.

Traditional uses for jute include treating aches and pains, fever, diarrhoea, enteritis, pectoral pains, and tumours. Ascites, discomfort, piles, cystitis, dysuria, gonorrhoea, and tumours are treated with leaves. It is stated that the cold infusion restores hunger and strength. Infusions are utilised to treat liver diseases and dyspepsia. Due to its high iron content, the leaf is an effective anti-anaemic that prevents anaemia and promotes the generation of red blood cells.

The jute leaf has long been used as a cure for pregnant women who are in labour for an extended period of time. It has also been shown to improve milk secretion in nursing women.

Corchorus olitorius aids in the treatment of premenstrual syndrome (PMS) and the regularity of the menstrual cycle. Researchers have also suggested that women going through menopause consume more of this vegetable.

The therapeutic and nutritional value of *Corchorus olitorius* (jute leaves) has inspired research into its chemical makeup and antioxidant effectiveness in the aim of uncovering new natural antioxidant sources.

Corchorus olitorius leaves are plentiful in phenolics and flavonoids, as well as having significant levels of antioxidant and antibacterial activity, according to newly identified chemicals discovered in research. Flavonoids are a class of natural low molecular weight phenolic chemicals found widely across the plant kingdom. They also exhibit a variety of biological properties, such as those linked

to anti-inflammatory, anti carcinogenic, antiviral, and anti oxidative properties (Faith, 2012). Because they can directly contribute to antioxidant effects within a cell, polyphenolic compounds, which are good electron donors and have distinct beneficial biological properties, have become natural components needed in the pharmaceutical and cosmetic industries.

Tannins have been demonstrated to prevent HIV replication, and their therapeutic qualities suggest that they could be used to treat a variety of diseases and improve human health (Ogunkanmi, 2010). However, study into the phytochemical contents of jute genotypes should aid in the development of a comprehensive understanding and perception of jute's medicinal and nutraceutical value, which could lead to increased consumption.

Plants provide the human body with negative vitamins, minerals, and positive hormone precursors, as well as protein and energy.

Corchoriolitorius plant consists of a considerable amount of Vitamin K which is helpful in reducing the threat of bleeding in the liver, poor nutrient absorption, jaundice or the combination of long term use of antibiotics or aspirin. Regular consumption of *jute* plant is believed to help slow the start of certain eye diseases, including age-related macular degeneration.

Corchoriolitorius plant consists of a sufficient amount of magnesium that is required for the body. Therefore frequent consumption is recommended to normalise asthma-related problems such as wheezing and breathless ness. *Corchoriolitorius* is said to lower blood pressure and cholesterol. It is good for heart health and diabetes, and can increase sexual libido and aid fertility. It is also a blood purifier and laxative Ngozika, O. (2020).

Figure 1. Jute leaf (*Corchoriolitorius*)

2. Materials and Methods

Materials

The materials used were: Albino Wister rats, weighing balance, feed, distilled water, rubber cages, water bath, lancet, sample chloroform, filter paper, dissecting kit, refrigerator, syringes and needle, a pair of scissors and forceps, randox glucose kit dissecting board, blood sample, methylated spirit (ethanol) *Corchorus olitorius* and one touch glucometer (Johnson-Johnson, company, China), Heparinized capillary tube, hematocrit centrifuge, hematocrit reader, thoma pipette, Turk's solution improved Neubauer counter, formaldehyde, sodium citrate, distilled water and microscope.

Collection of Plant Sample

Fresh *Corchoriolitorius* samples were collected from Bwari market, Bwari area council Abuja. The sample was collected, washed, and blended. The sample weighing Xg was soaked in 2000ml of absolute methanol for 48hours after which it was filtered using a Whattman filter paper No. 1. The filtrate was concentrated using rotary evaporator at 40°C and further concentrated using a thermostatic water bath at 40°C. The concentrate was then collected in sterile amber bottles and stored at 4°C until administration begins.

Preparation of Extract

The plant sample (leaves) was washed and air dried, pulverized and soaked for 48 hours in 95% methanol. The

Pulverized sample was sieved (about 0.5mm) using a muslin cloth and then Whattman filter paper. The filtered

Sample was extracted using Soxhlet Extractor. The extract was transferred into the beaker which was finally placed in a water bath at 35°C to reduce the moisture content. The extract obtained was stored in clean sample bottles at 4°C until usage.

Animals

Thirty albino wistar rats were used for the experiment. The thirty adult Wister rats were obtained from an animal Farm in Kaduna State, Nigeria. The rats were housed in the Animal House of Veritas University Abuja to acclimatize for two weeks. While being acclimatized, rats were fed with standard rat feed and deionized water and maintained at standard laboratory conditions of 12 hours light/12 hours dark periodic alternations, temperature: 22-28°C and 40-50% relative humidity. The rats were randomly selected two days to the commencement of the experiment and allocated into five (5) groups. The first groups were control group, second to the fifth groups, were given extract according to their body weight. They were 6 each per Group. The rats in each group were fed with Growers' feed mash (Top Growers feed Ltd Nigeria) and water ad libitum.

Extract Administration

On day one of the experiment, the five groups were allocated into their various groups in such a way that the difference in body weight within and between members of a particular group does not exceed $\pm 20\%$ of the average weight of sample population of rats. The five groups' rats were orally given specific measurements of required feed, water and extract.

Table 1. Experimental Design

Rat groups	Group title	Extract administered
Group E	Normal control	distilled water
Group A	Administration group one	100mg/kg of <i>Corchorus olitorius</i> plant extract.
Group B	Administrator group two	150mg/kg of <i>Corchorus olitorius</i> plant extract.

Group C	Administration group three	250mg/kg of <i>Corchorus olitorius</i> plant extract.
Group D	Administration group four	300mg/kg of <i>Corchorus olitorius</i> plant extract.

Animal Sacrifice and collection of samples for analysis

At the end of the 14-day period, the rats were deprived of food but had access to water during the night. They were then sacrificed and euthanized using chloroform vapour. Rats had a midline incision made in the anterior abdominal wall. Blood was extracted from the heart using sterilised syringes and needles to puncture the heart. From the descending abdominal aorta, 5ml of blood samples were taken in Heparin anticoagulant tubes for haematological examination.

Hematological Indices

Evaluation of Hematological parameters

Hematological variables the white blood cell and packed cell volume (PCV) counts were determined by hand. The obtained results are precise (error of measurement is lower than 1%) and are manually compared with standard values for individual parameters.

White Blood cells (WBC)

Blood was collected using a syringe from the descending abdominal aorta from albino Wistar rats into a Heparinized sample bottle 0.02ml of the blood was diluted into 0.38ml of Turks solution and that gave one in twenty dilutions (1:20) using a Thomas pipette. The Thomas pipette is marked to give 0.02ml of blood after diluting the blood, the improved Neubauer counting chamber is then changed with a drop diluted blood and covered with a glass cover slip and then placed on the microscope and viewed using x10 objective lens. The four large squares placed at the corner of the chamber was counted using a tally counter since the concentration of the counteraction of white blood cells are lower than red blood cells so a larger area will be used.

Calculations for white blood cells

For white Blood cells, the number of cells counted was calculated as thus;

Number of cells counted = $1/\text{Area of counting chamber} \times 1/\text{depth of counting chamber} \times \text{dilution factor}$

Number of cells counted = A cells counted x a known constant

Number of cells counted = A cells/ mm³

Note: The improved Neubauer counting chamber has a known depth and area a given constant is given.

Packed cell volume (PCV)

Blood was collected using a syringe from the heart of albino wistar rats into Heparinized sample bottle. The blood was then collected using a Heparinized capillary tube to about $\frac{3}{4}$ full of the Heparinized capillary tube. After collection the Heparinized tube was then sealed by passing it through flame using a burden burner. When sealing was completed the capillary tube was then placed

on the hematocrit centrifuge and spun at 5000revolution per minute for 5 minutes. When spinning was completed, the capillary tube then separated into their components; the buffy coat, plasma and the red cells, it's the uppermost part of the red cells that was read using a hematocrit reader.

3. Results

The results obtained from the Haematological and Phytochemical analysis of the plant extract are shown in the tables below.

Table 2. Phytochemical constituent of *Corchorus Oilitorius* plant extract

Flavonoids	+
Terpenoids	+
Tannins	+
Quinones	+
Steroids	-
Phenols	+

Key; (+) = present and (-) = Not detected

Table 3. Packed cell volume and white blood cell.

GROUPS	PCV%	WBC/L
A	48.50 ± 1.72 ^a	14683.33 ± 2975.16 ^a
B	41.00 ± 8.22 ^a	14558.33 ± 2981.28 ^a
C	26.66 ± 11.95 ^a	8883.33 ± 4026.53 ^a
D	42.83 ± 8.72 ^a	15833.33 ± 3305.92 ^a
E	33.16 ± 10.63 ^a	12183.33 ± 3907.12 ^b

Values are expressed as Mean + — SEM at significant level of $p < 0.05$ where $n=5$.

Values on the same column with the same super script are statistically not different. Whereas values on the same column with different super script are significantly different.

The effect of methanolic extract of *Corchorusolitorius* on Chloride concentration on Wistar Rats.

The chloride concentration in groups A, B, C, and E administered 100, 150, 250and 300 mg/kg b.w. of the extract, respectively, was not significant at ($p < 0.05$) compared to the normal control group.

Figure 2. Chloride concentration in different experimental groups. Values are expressed as Mean + SEM at significant level of $p < 0.05$ where $n=5$.

The effect of methanolic extract of *Corchoriosolitorius* on Potassium concentration in Wistar Rats. There was a non-significant difference at ($p < 0.05$) in potassium concentration when compared to the control group.

Figure 3. Potassium concentration in different experimental groups. Values are expressed as Mean + SEM at significant level of $p < 0.05$ where $n=5$.

The effect of methanolic extract of *Corchoriosolitorius* on Sodium concentration in Albino Wistar Rats.

The concentration of sodium in groups A, B, C, and D administered 100, 150, 250, and 300 mg/kg b.w. of the extract, respectively, was significant at ($p < 0.05$) compared with the normal group.

Figure 4. Sodium concentration levels in different experimental groups. Values are expressed as Mean + SEM at significant level of $p < 0.05$ where $n=5$.

4. Discussion

The presence of active components such as tannins, terpenoids, quinones, phenols, and flavonoids was discovered during phytochemical screening of *Corchorus olitorius* leaf extract. These phytochemicals have been shown to have therapeutic properties, justifying their usage in traditional medicine. These phytoconstituents may be responsible for a variety of pharmacological activities, including wound healing, cholesterol reduction, and antidiabetic activity.

Typically, plant antioxidants are categorised as secondary metabolic products (Sharmila et al.2007). When oxygen is partially reduced, reactive oxygen species (ROS) such as superoxide anion (O_2^-), hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), and hydroxyl radical (HO^\bullet) are produced. These molecules protect cells from the harmful effects of reactive oxygen species (ROS) such as superoxide anion (O_2^-), hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), and hydroxyl radical (Siddique and Alim, 2013). ROS can be generated endogenously as a byproduct of mitochondrial oxidative phosphorylation, or exogenously as a result of interactions with exogenous sources such as xenobiotic substances. An imbalance between antioxidants and reactive oxygen species (ROS) causes oxidative stress in cells, which leads to cellular spoilage (Siddique and Alim, 2013). This condition is frequently associated to physiological issues such as cancer, aging, and atherosclerosis. The existence of several secondary metabolites and antioxidants was discovered in the present investigation of phytochemical screening and antioxidant activity of methanolic extract of *Corchorus olitorius* leaves. Because of the existence of these bioactive substances in jute leaf, it can be utilized as a natural therapeutic agent to treat a variety of infections and other disorders. *Corchorus olitorius* is widely available and inexpensive, therefore it can be used for therapeutic purposes with few or no adverse effects when compared to conventional drugs (Siddique and Alim, 2013).

Electrolytes are important in a variety of bodily functions, including fluid balance, acid-base balance (pH), nerve conduction, coagulation, and muscular contraction (Hasona and Elsbali, 2016). Homeostasis of fluid and electrolytes is normally maintained within strict limitations (Roberts, 2005), therefore it must be maintained at a level that is appropriate for proper biochemical and physiological processes (Kaneko *et al.*, 2008).

The sodium ion is a critical Extracellular Fluid electrolyte that is involved in a variety of physiological processes, including depolarization of excitable tissues, neuron function, and osmoregulation between cells and the extracellular fluid, with its distribution mediated by Na^+/K^+ -ATPase in all animals.

The non-significant drop in serum sodium in animals treated with *Corchorus olitorius* extract could be due to the high sodium (Na⁺) content of *Corchorus olitorius*, which may have contributed to the low levels detected in the rats' serum.

Potassium is a vital intracellular mineral that helps people and animals maintain fluid and electrolyte balance in their bodies. Hypokalemia is caused by abnormal potassium regulation. The considerable increase in serum potassium level found in this study could be due to the fact that *Corchorus olitorius* contains more potassium than sodium, which could explain for the elevated potassium level. This conclusion backed up Seifter's report.

This means that increasing intake of *Corchorus olitorius* can lead to a build-up of potassium in the body, which can lead to hyperkalemia.

The results of our current investigation demonstrate an increase in chloride concentration when compared to the control group. The reason for this is that the serum chloride level in *Corchorusolitorius* was found to be higher in this investigation. This means that consuming more *Corchorus olitorius* can cause a build-up of chloride in the body, which could lead to hyperchlorenemia.

Hematological indices can be used to detect or determine the extent of a foreign compound's harmful influence on an animal's blood constituents, including plant extracts and products (Evabakhavbon et al., 2020). The purpose of this study was to assess the haematological indices (such as white blood cell count and packed cell volume) of rats given varied doses of *Corchorus Oilitorius*.

The outcome of this study showed that packed cell volume of wistar rats treated with *Corchorus Oilitorius* has no significant difference at ($p < 0.05$) within the test groups. This indicates the non toxic nature of the plant to the Red blood cells.

The results in the study also revealed a significant difference in the white blood cells (WBC) of normal group in comparison with those treated with the leaf extract of *Corchorus olitorius* which was significant at ($p < 0.05$). The sudden surge of white blood cell count in the administration group is consistent with the previous findings of (O.F et al., 2014). This could be attributed to the presence of phytochemical compounds. This compound is a good anti-anaemic, which prevent anemia due to its high iron content and facilitate the production of red blood cells Ngozika, O. (2020). The result of this study is in conformity with Okoye et al. (2013), who stated that *CoruchorusOilitorius* plant properties contained active component (phytochemical) and biological activities which include anti-anaemic, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti – aging and immune modulatory.

5. Conclusion

The result of the study shows that *Corchorus olitorius* (*ewedu* leaf) contains significant amount of photochemical properties that can boost the immune system and thus defend the body against diseases. Also, from the results above, *Corchorus olitorius* possesses natural therapeutic potential, haemopoietic properties and maintaining body homeostasis of fluid and electrolytes.

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